

PROJECT: Smart Home Security System

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LINKS TO WEBSITES USED IN OUR PROJECT

- ThingSpeak: <https://thingspeak.mathworks.com/channels/3348172>
- SupaBase: <https://smart-home-security-syst-2d94a-default-rtdb.europe-west1.firebaseio.com/>
- Google Colab: <https://colab.research.google.com/drive/1gkZr3-1IhZkkrVN3PQwECeVOE75NzOFJ#scrollTo=patch>
- Smart_Home_Dashboard: https://blesngesera.github.io/SmartHomeSecurity_Wokwi/smart_home_dashboard.html